

№3 / 2025

ANDIJON DAVLAT PEDAGOGIKA INSTITUTI

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№ 3 2025

Jurnal 2023-yildan chop etilmoqda

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy
kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan
2022-yil 25-oktyabrda
№ 045013 raqam bilan ro'yxatga olingan
ISSN 2181-4309

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va
innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi
Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi
Rayosatining 2024-yil 8-maydagi
№354-sonli qarori bilan
Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha Oliy attestatsiya
komissiyasining dissertatsiyalar asosiy ilmiy
natijalarini chop etish tavsiya etilgan ilmiy nashrlar
ro'yxatiga kiritilgan.

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применение данной методики привело к значительному увеличению показателей моральной устойчивости и способности к принятию решений в условиях неопределённости.

Важно отметить, что особую роль в формировании морально-психологической устойчивости сыграли командные тренинги и методы психологической сплочённости. Коллективное взаимодействие военнослужащих в стрессовых ситуациях позволяет не только укрепить командный дух, но и способствует формированию взаимной поддержки и доверия внутри подразделения. Как отмечают G.Rubin и K.Thomas, высокая степень сплочённости подразделения напрямую связана с его боевой эффективностью и моральной устойчивостью [7]. Результаты нашего исследования подтверждают это: в экспериментальной группе наблюдалось значительное улучшение показателей групповой сплочённости и межличностных взаимоотношений.

Несмотря на полученные позитивные результаты, следует отметить и некоторые ограничения проведённого исследования. Во-первых, выборка была представлена преимущественно курсантами военной академии, что ограничивает возможность экстраполяции данных на более широкий круг военнослужащих, находящихся в различных условиях службы. Во-вторых, исследование длилось шесть месяцев, что является достаточным сроком для выявления краткосрочных эффектов, но требует дальнейшего наблюдения за долгосрочной устойчивостью полученных изменений.

Разработанная методическая технология организации МПП позволяет значительно повысить морально-психологическую устойчивость военнослужащих. В ходе эксперимента показана её эффективность, что подтверждается статистическими данными.

Перспективы дальнейших исследований связаны с адаптацией технологии к условиям боевого дежурства и изучением её влияния на боевую эффективность военнослужащих.

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UO'K. 420.12

RESEARCH ON THE NATIONAL AESTHETICS OF CHINESE PIANO WORKS

<https://zenodo.org/records/15776435>

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Abstract. *The national aesthetics of Chinese piano works is a unique embodiment of the fusion of Chinese and Western music cultures, and it demonstrates the artistic wisdom and cultural heritage of the Chinese nation. This paper takes "the national aesthetics of Chinese piano works" as the research object, and discusses it from two levels: national aesthetic characteristics and aesthetic interpretation. In terms*

of performance technology, the unique expressiveness of national music is reflected through the delicate processing of melody lines, the color presentation of national harmony, the simulation and shaping of timbre, and the elastic grasp of rhythm; in terms of emotional expression, the works not only focus on the creation of traditional lyrical artistic conception, but also show the national cultural spirit through a variety of creative themes. The study shows that the national aesthetics of Chinese piano works is rooted in the deep soil of traditional music culture, and is constantly innovating in the context of modern music, forming an artistic expression that is both national and cosmopolitan. This study is of great significance for understanding the aesthetic value of Chinese piano music and promoting the modern expression of national music.

Key words: *Chinese piano works, national culture, national aesthetics, artistic conception, innovating in the context.*

Annotatsiya. *Xitoy pianino asarlarining milliy estetikasi Xitoy va G'arb musiqa madaniyati uyg'unligining o'ziga xos timsoli bo'lib, u Xitoy xalqining badiiy va madaniy merosini namoyish etadi. Ushbu maqola tadqiqot ob'ekti sifatida "xitoylik pianino asarlarining milliy estetikasi"ni o'z ichiga oladi va uni ta'limdagi o'rni haqida mushohada qiladi: milliy estetik xususiyatlar va estetik talqinning tarbiyadagi ahamiyati ko'rib chiqiladi. Ijro texnologiyasi nuqtai nazaridan milliy musiqaning o'ziga xos ifodaliligi ohang satrlariga nozik ishlov berish, milliy garmoniyaning rang-barang ifodalanishi, tembrni o'xshatish va shakllantirish, ritmni elastik idrok etish orqali namoyon bo'ladi; tuyg'u ifodasi jihatidan asarlar nafaqat an'anaviy lirik badiiy konsepsiya yaratishga qaratilgan, balki turli ijodiy mavzular orqali milliy madaniy ruhni namoyon etadi. Tadqiqotlarimiz shuni ko'rsatadiki, xitoy pianino asarlarining milliy estetikasi an'anaviy musiqa madaniyatining teran tuprog'iga borib taqaladi va zamonaviy musiqa kontekstida muttasil yangilanib turadi, ham milliy, ham kosmopolit badiiy ifodani shakllantiradi. Ushbu tadqiqot Xitoy pianino musiqasining estetik qiymatini tushunish va milliy musiqaning zamonaviy ifodasini targ'ib qilishda katta ahamiyatga ega.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Xitoy pianino asarlari, milliy madaniyat, milliy estetika, badiiy kontsepsiya, kontekstda innovatsiya.*

Аннотация. *Национальная эстетика китайских фортепианных произведений является уникальным воплощением слияния китайской и западной музыкальных культур, и она демонстрирует художественную мудрость и культурное наследие китайской нации. В этой статье в качестве объекта исследования рассматривается «национальная эстетика китайских фортепианных произведений», и она обсуждается на двух уровнях: национальные эстетические характеристики и эстетическая интерпретация. С точки зрения технологии исполнения уникальная выразительность национальной музыки отражается через тонкую обработку мелодических линий, цветовое представление национальной гармонии, моделирование и формирование тембра и эластичное схватывание ритма; с точки зрения эмоционального выражения произведения не только сосредоточены на создании традиционной лирической художественной концепции, но и показывают национальный культурный дух через различные творческие темы. Исследование показывает, что национальная эстетика китайских фортепианных произведений коренится в глубокой почве традиционной музыкальной культуры и постоянно обновляется в контексте современной музыки, формируя художественное выражение, которое является как национальным, так и космополитичным. Это исследование имеет большое значение для понимания эстетической ценности китайской фортепианной музыки и продвижения современного выражения национальной музыки.*

Ключевые слова: *Китайские фортепианные произведения, национальная культура, национальная эстетика, художественная концепция, новаторство в контексте.*

The development of Chinese piano music has gone through nearly a century. As a representative of Western polyphonic instruments, the piano is known as the "king of musical instruments". Due to its rich timbre and wide range, it can imitate and adapt almost all other musical forms. The difference between Chinese and Western piano music creation lies in the different foundations of musical culture. Chinese music is a pentatonic mode based on the fifth-tone law, while Western music is a major and minor mode based on the twelve-tone equal temperament. As a foreign instrument, the piano has continued the characteristics of linear

melody of Chinese music in the process of integration and intersection with Chinese national culture, forming a harmonic mode that interweaves Western traditional harmony and Chinese national mode, borrowing and imitating the musical language with Chinese characteristics, retaining the color and charm of the national pentatonic mode, and thus continuously forming the creation techniques of piano music with Chinese characteristics. In many piano music works adapted from Chinese ancient music and national instrumental music, the audience can still feel the strong charm of Chinese music, and the piano has also given Chinese traditional music a new artistic life, so that Chinese national music and national culture have been further promoted and carried forward. Many pianists and composers in my country, while absorbing the essence of Western piano art, have also continuously integrated Chinese traditional culture and art, and created many excellent piano works with Chinese national characteristics. These works not only combine the creative techniques of Western piano, but also display the aesthetic characteristics of Chinese traditional culture and have extremely high artistic value.

The Chinese nation is a nation with a long history and profound traditional cultural heritage. The traditional culture of a nation originates from the life, customs, characteristics and spirit of a nation. The culture of the Chinese nation is mainly Confucian culture and Taoist culture. The two cultures are mutually integrated and have a certain degree of tolerance. Any culture has its positive side and its negative side. The characteristics and spirit of the Chinese nation are constantly enriched and developed under the positive cultural background. Piano, like other arts, is closely related to the life, customs, characteristics and spirit of a nation [1].

First, it expresses national culture. Chinese piano works have incorporated more national culture in the creation process, realizing the localization of piano art. my country is a multi-ethnic country, and each ethnic group has formed a very distinctive national culture in the course of development, including lifestyles, religious beliefs, and ideological values. Composers often incorporate these national customs into their creations. For example, Ding Shande's "First Xinjiang Dance" was created in combination with the Xinjiang Uyghur folk dance work "The Coachman's Song"; Huang Huwei's "Paintings of Bashu" was created using Sichuan's traditional folk music and cultural elements, expressing the unique customs and customs of Bashu.

Second, it absorbs popular culture. The creation of Chinese piano works is often guided by the public's aesthetic needs, reflecting the public's daily life, and stimulating the public's emotional resonance, so as to increase the popularity and influence of piano works. Most of its musical materials come from real life, which is closely related to the public's daily life, and also reflects the public's higher aesthetic pursuit. For example, Wang Jianzhong's adaptations of "Colorful Clouds Chasing the Moon" and "Three Variations on Plum Blossoms" are based on traditional Chinese music works and are adapted with the aesthetic orientation of contemporary people. The works not only contain rich national charm, but are also closely related to the lives of the public. They can play the positive role of piano art in cultivating sentiment and improving the public's aesthetic level.

The third is to integrate into the culture of the times. The development of Chinese piano art is based on the continuous integration of the culture of the times. The first is to keep up with the times. Chinese piano art was introduced in the late Qing Dynasty and kept up with the development of the National Revolution, the Anti-Japanese War, the Liberation War, socialist construction, and reform and opening up. It created a large number of cultural works that reflect the lives of the people and express their emotions, which are full of the spirit of the times [2]. For example, works such as "Variations on Chinese Folk Song Themes" and "Beijing Wanhua

Collection" show the characteristics of the development of the times. The second is to absorb advanced Western culture. For example, "Sunset Xiaogu" was created based on Western piano techniques and integrated with traditional Chinese instruments.

For music works, "melody" is a prominent feature of Chinese piano works. In melody creation, in order to reflect the original national characteristics and the characteristics of ethnic folk songs, the timbre of different piano ranges is often used in a unique way to make the tone change. For example, Wang Jianzhong used changing melodies in his works "Guessing Tune" and "Dragon Lantern Tune" to reflect the humorous and lively artistic conception.

First, make full use of the melody of the pentatonic mode. The three-tone group is the basis of the mode. This three-tone group is composed of a minor third and a major second. The core of the organization is the melody of the Chinese pentatonic mode, and the Chinese beauty tone expressed is pentatonic. For example, the piano work "Liuyang River" retains the national characteristics of the original tune while using the sound wave technique 7 times to produce the image of sparkling and rippling waves. The scenery of Hunan is fully reflected, fully reflecting the oriental Chinese beauty from all angles.

Second, use ornaments and special playing methods. In the process of music creation, in order to integrate national charm and national feelings into the creation of piano music, a large number of ornaments are used to beautify the color of the melody [3]. For example, the piano piece "Hundred Birds Paying Homage to the Phoenix" uses a large number of ornaments. Through creative ornaments, dissonance, semitone progression and other piano textures, the traditional piano playing techniques are combined with new timbre techniques to vividly depict various bird calls and vividly reproduce the fun of suona playing methods. The playing of short grace notes should be fast and powerful, imitating the sound of birds singing; the playing of long vibrato should express the melodious singing of birds.

In Chinese piano works, melody is an important factor in expressing its national characteristics. In the process of piano performance, the performer needs to have an overall grasp of the melody of the work and interpret the work in combination with his own subjective understanding. Such piano performance is a performance after "inner singing", and its performance will be more fluent and the expression of emotions will be more real. Pentatonic harmony is a prominent feature of Chinese folk music and an important feature that distinguishes Chinese piano music from Western music. In the performance of national piano works, national modes and scales are issues that should be considered in fingering practice. In the creation of national works, many composers draw on the musical melodies of their own nation. For example, "Shepherd's Flute" uses the "double sentence" method of national music to enhance its national color.

The second is harmony. The nationality of Chinese piano works has many requirements for harmony. In order to meet the national characteristics of piano works, Chinese piano composers often borrow some nationalized harmonies to strengthen their national colors, such as the superimposed harmony of the second or fourth degree. For example, in "A Hundred Birds Paying Homage to the Phoenix", the composer used the overlapping of minor second harmonics to create an atmosphere, showing the spectacular scene of hundreds of birds singing, giving people an immersive feeling. The work "Sunset Flute and Drum" uses the harmony of the second, fourth and fifth degrees to create a harmonious and orderly artistic conception.

The third is timbre. Different musical instruments have different timbres. In piano performance, although the performer can use different keys to express relatively different

timbres, it is still limited by the structure and material of the piano itself when interpreting national piano music works. Therefore, it is very important to use the timbre of the piano itself to show rich and distinctive national colors. Chinese piano composers often use ornaments to show vivid national music content and strengthen the national color of the work. The work "Sunset Xiaogu" uses a large number of ornaments to imitate the timbre of traditional instruments such as guzheng and pipa, and some octave appoggiatura are used to make the piano produce a timbre similar to that of the flute.

The fourth is rhythm. Rhythm is also an important influencing factor in the creation of piano music works, and its expression effect is relatively direct. In the process of the nationalization of Chinese piano music, rhythm is often a necessary factor that musicians consider when creating. The rhythm of the work "Folk Songs and Bronze Drum Music" is very distinct. At the same time, it also uses the intervals commonly used in Guangxi national music to enhance the rhythm of the work, giving the work a national color [4].

The first is lyrical emotion. Chinese piano works largely express the introverted emotions and implicit character of the Chinese nation. Chinese piano works often express emotions through the expression of emotional blending. The "scenery" in it is not the scenery in the objective sense, but a good environmental atmosphere. Through this atmosphere and the expression of emotions, the music works are perfectly interpreted. The work "Erquan Yingyue" is a typical example of the successful use of the expression method of scene blending. This work mainly describes the scenery, uses unique musical techniques to create an environmental atmosphere that conforms to the style of the work, and expresses A Bing's life experience by expressing sad emotions, so that the audience is immersed in this sad emotional atmosphere.

The second is the theme of creation. The development of Chinese piano music is based on national culture. Whether it is adaptation or original work, the fundamental purpose is to show the connotation of Chinese traditional culture. Among them, patriotism is an eternal theme in the creation of Chinese piano works. Some key historical events are integrated into piano creation. For example, "Ode to the Yellow River" was created based on the war years. It describes the deeds of the Chinese people who continued to struggle for national liberation and national independence during the war years, and praises their strong patriotic enthusiasm and fighting spirit; there are also some that take praising the beautiful mountains and rivers of the motherland as the creative theme, and express the love for the motherland through the depiction of natural scenery. For example, "Flowing Stream" uses a variety of embellishments to show the natural scenery of the countryside, and then praises the beautiful mountains and rivers of the motherland.

With its unique national aesthetic characteristics, Chinese piano works have constructed an artistic expression system with oriental charm in the fusion of Chinese and Western music cultures. This study systematically examines the national aesthetic characteristics of Chinese piano works and their interpretation methods through theoretical analysis and practical exploration. The study found that in terms of aesthetic characteristics, Chinese piano works show the connotation of national culture through three dimensions: they not only deeply express the essence of traditional music, but also widely absorb the nutrients of folk popular culture, and actively integrate the cultural characteristics of the times; in terms of musical language, the works creatively use the pentatonic tuning system, and draw on the ornaments and special playing methods of national instruments to form a melody feature that is different from Western piano music. At the level of aesthetic interpretation, the nationalization of

performance technology is particularly critical, including the delicate carving of melody lines, the color presentation of national harmony, the simulation and shaping of timbre, and the elastic grasp of rhythm. These technical means jointly construct the unique sound world of Chinese piano music. In terms of emotional expression, the works not only focus on the creation of traditional lyrical artistic conception, but also show the national cultural spirit through a variety of creative themes, realizing the organic unity of technicality and artistry. This study not only reveals the internal logic of the national aesthetics of Chinese piano works, but also provides a theoretical reference for the national performance and teaching of piano art [5]. In the future, the creation and development of Chinese piano works still need to further explore the deep integration of tradition and modernity on the basis of maintaining national characteristics, and promote the piano art with Chinese national characteristics to the world stage. This exploration is not only a creative transformation of traditional culture, but also an important contribution to the diversity of world music culture.

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UO'K: 378.091.31:811:796

IMPROVING THE COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION STUDENTS THROUGH ORGANIZING ENGLISH CLASSES OUTSIDE THE AUDITORY

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Abstract. *This article explores the methodological and pedagogical foundations of improving the communicative competence of physical education students by organizing English language lessons outside the classroom. The paper analyzes the potential of outdoor and practice-oriented learning environments to enhance language skills in context-specific situations, drawing on international experiences and integrative pedagogical approaches.*

Key words: *Communicative competence, physical education students, outdoor learning, English language teaching, integrative approach, experiential learning.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada jismoniy madaniyat yo'nalishi talabalari kommunikativ kompetensiyasini auditoriyadan tashqarida ingliz tili darslarini tashkil etish orqali rivojlantirishning metodik va pedagogik asoslari tahlil qilinadi. Maqolada xalqaro tajribalar va integrativ pedagogik yondashuvlarga tayangan holda kontekstga xos vaziyatlarda til ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda ochiq va amaliy yo'naltirilgan ta'lim muhitlarining salohiyati o'rganiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *kommunikativ kompetensiya, jismoniy madaniyat yo'nalishi talabalari, auditoriyadan tashqari ta'lim, ingliz tilini o'qitish, integrativ yondashuv, tajriba asosida o'qitish.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются методологические и педагогические основы повышения коммуникативной компетенции студентов направления "Физическая культура" посредством организации занятий по английскому языку вне аудитории. Анализируется потенциал внеаудиторной и практико-ориентированной образовательной среды*

